

The health-protecting efficacy of four formulated plant-based diets on rats exposed to particulate organic matters (POPs)

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ABSTRACT

The widespread of pollutants in our environment coupled with the failure of conventional pollution management strategies, has led to the search for effective individual-based solutions. This study evaluates the health-protecting efficacy of four formulated plant-based diets in the blood of albino rats exposed to particulate organic matters (POPs). Albino rats grouped into five containing 10 rats each were exposed to POPs at about 200 m from a dump site in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria. Group one was the control and groups two through five formed the test rats. The gross morphology and the blood parameters of all the rats were measured before commencing the study and served as the baseline indices. The test rats were then fed ad libitum with plant-based diets containing basil, moringa turmeric, and cloves, respectively, for 3 weeks. The control rats received normal pelletized feeds without the formulated diets for the same duration. The rats were observed daily and at the end of the treatment, the blood parameters were measured again. The control rats significantly lost weight, while the test rats significantly gained weights. The control rats were anemic with lymphopenia and monocytosis, while the blood parameters of the test rats showed no abnormal condition. These findings showed the formulated diets protected the health of the exposed rats. As such, people are advised to include these tested plants in their diets to prevent or ameliorative the effects of pollutants.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Pollutants are chemicals or substances, which, when released can cause undesirable changes in the environment, making it dirty and unsafe or unsuitable for living organisms. Most pollutants come from energy use and production, fossil fuels burning, for example, releases enormous gases and chemicals into the air [1]. Pollutants can be classified as toxic or nontoxic depending on the severity or otherwise of its health effects. It can also be classified based on the type of health effects it causes. Thus, pollutants can be carcinogenic (e.g. some volatile organic compounds) or biologically active (e.g. some viruses) or radioactive (e.g. radon). Other pollutants like carbon dioxide have an indirect impact on human health through climate change [2]. Pollutants in the air, water or soil can cause acute illnesses, such as respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, multi-organ injuries and cancers, and neuro-developmental and

hormonal disorders [3]. They may also cause other illnesses such as birth defects, low IQ, reduced life expectancy, among others [2].

Since the Industrial Revolution started in the late 18th century, large quantities of pollutants have been released into the environment, causing a lot of chronic diseases and death [4]. For example, in 1984, the release of methyl isocyanate gas at Union Carbide plant in Bhopal killed over 2,000 people, and over 200,000 suffered respiratory problems [2]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), ambient air pollution alone contributes to about 6.7 percent of all deaths worldwide. The organization also linked about 7 million premature deaths annually to air pollution alone, translating to one in every eight deaths worldwide. This is far more than the number of deaths due to HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, and malaria combined [5]. It has also been estimated that both air, land and water pollution

combined cause an annual death of about 9 millions, mostly in developing countries [6]. Furthermore, pollution contributes to disabling conditions in millions of people, including asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and cardiovascular problems [5]. Economically, effects of pollutants and pollution management have caused a great setback to national development globally as it gulp a great chunk of the annual budget. For instance, it was estimated that premature mortality associated with air pollution alone costs US\$ 225 billion in lost labor income or more than US\$5 trillion in welfare losses worldwide in 2013 [7]. Between 2009 and 2016, World Bank commitments to pollution management and environmental health totaled approximately US\$ 6.5 billion [8]. All these monies could have been used to improve the human standard of living worldwide.

Certainly, industrialization has caused enormous damage to lives and the environment through emission of various pollutants. However, it cannot be stopped or reversed because it has come with a lot of benefits too.

Industrialization has made socioeconomic activities easier through the use of machines and changed the world from a predominantly agrarian to an industrial one where people work in factories and earn money. As a result of this, it is necessary to ameliorate the health consequences of various industrial pollutants in order to create a sustainable development where industries grow unhindered and human health is not compromised. Various organizations, including the World Bank and WHO is committed to a safe and clean environment, however, it seems conventional pollution management needs to be complemented with individual-based approaches. Therefore, the aim of the study was to find effective plant-based diets that could ameliorate the effects of pollutants, particularly POPs.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Animal material

A total of 50 albino rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) weighing between 200 and 250 g were purchased from the Usmanun Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria. The rats were made to acclimatize to the ambient environments for seven days before commencing the research.

2.2 Animal feed

A bag of palletized animal feed from the F. A Feeds industry, were used in the diets formulation.

2.3 Plant material

Four plant species, namely basil (*Ocimum basilicum*), moringa (*Moringa oleifera*), turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) and cloves (*Syngizium*

aromaticum) were purchased from a market in Birnin Kebbi and used for the study. The food plants were identified in the Department of Biology, Federal University Birnin Kebbi.

2.4 Formulation of the diets

About 500 g of each plant material was washed gently to remove impurities and then crushed in a mortar. The bioactive components were thereafter extracted in a 300 ml of water and poured into a crucible dish. The crucible dish was put in an oven and kept at 38°C and dried till a constant weight was obtained. Each dried plant extract obtained was mixed thoroughly and individually with the animal feed in the ratio 1:4 (i.e. 1 part of each plant extract to 4 parts of the animal feed). The formulated diets were then stored in desiccators before use.

2.5 Acute toxicity test

The acute toxicity of the formulated diets was measured using the 'Classical LD₅₀' method described by Gabriel *et al.* [9]. Albino rats (36) of both sexes weighing between 200 and 205 g were used for the studies. The rats were randomly distributed into six groups of 6 rats each and were made to fast for 12 hours before commencing the study. The rats in the test groups were orally administered 200, 400, 500, 700, 1500 and 2000 mg kg⁻¹ doses of the formulated diets. The control rats were fed with only distilled water. The general symptoms of toxicity were monitored and recorded for each group within 24 hours.

2.6 Study design

The albino rats were grouped into 5 of 10 rats each. The control rats were placed in group one, while groups two through five contained the test rats. The blood samples of some of the rats were collected and blood parameters measured before exposure and served as the baseline indices on which the effects of the diets were evaluated. The entire rats were then exposed to POPs at a distance of about 200 m from a dump site in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria. The test rats were fed *ad libitum*, along with water, formulated diets of basil, moringa, turmeric and cloves, respectively, for 3 weeks. The control rats were given only normal palletized feeds and distilled water for the same duration. The gross morphological changes of the rats were monitored daily and the blood parameters measured again at the end of the exposure.

2.7 Measurement of blood parameters

The rats were sedated with chloroform in a bell glass jar in the laboratory. Total death was prevented to allow continuous flow of blood for proper blood collection. Each rat was pegged down on a work bench and held firmly with office pins. Surgical blades were used to cut through the chest region of the rats in a dorsal-ventral direction. The blood was then collected

from a beating heart using a Na Heparinized capillary tube through capillary action into EDTA bottles. EDTA serves as an anti-coagulant and so Na heparin in the capillary tube. The blood parameters were determined using Sysmex auto-analyzer.

2.8 Statistical analysis

A database file was created on a personal computer. All statistical analysis was carried out using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21 for Windows and Microsoft Office Excel 2007. Comparisons of data between control and test groups were calculated using Student's t-test. The $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Acute toxicity test

The acute toxicity test showed the formulated diets were nontoxic to the rats even at a dose of 2000 mg kg⁻¹. No mortality was recorded and none of the rats show any sign of illnesses. The rats were eager to take the formulated diets.

3.2 Effects of the formulated diets on the weight of the exposed rats

Table 1 shows the effects of the formulated diets on the weights of the exposed rats. The control rats lost about -18 g weight at the end of the exposure, while the test rats gained considerable weights. Turmeric diet fed rats had the highest weight gain of about 23 g and the rats fed cloves diet had the least with about 12 g.

Table 1. Variation in the weights (g) of the exposed rats.

Group	Day 0	Day 28	Mean Change
Control	260 ^a ± 2.7	242 ^b ± 2.5	-18 ± 0.2
Basil	261 ^a ± 2.2	280 ^b ± 2.4	19 ± 0.2
Moringa	262 ^a ± 3.2	282 ^b ± 2.9	20 ± 0.3
Turmeric	260 ^a ± 2.8	283 ^b ± 3.2	23 ± 0.4
Cloves	263 ^a ± 3.1	275 ^a ± 4.0	12 ± 0.9

Data are expressed as Mean ± SE;

Mean values with different superscripts 'a' and 'b' along the same row are significantly different at $P < 0.05$.

3.3 Effects of the formulated diets on the blood parameters of the exposed rats

Tables 2-7 show the protective efficacy of the formulated diets on the selected blood parameters of the exposed rats. In table 2, the control rats had -11 % decrease in the PCV, whereas the rats fed with basil, moringa, turmeric and cloves diets had -5, -3, -1, and 4 % decrease, respectively. Table 3 shows the HB decrease of the control rats is -3.7 g/dL, while the HB decrease of the rats fed basil, moringa, turmeric and cloves are - 1.7, -1.3, - 01 and -1.8 g/dL, respectively. The RBC decrease of the control rats is -1.91 mc/mcL, whereas the rats administered basil, moringa, turmeric and closes

had RBC decrease of - 0.90, -1.12, - 0.49 and - 0.49 mc/mcL, respectively (Table 4). In table 5, the control rats had -1, 150 c/mcL decrease in WBC, while the rats fed basil, moringa, turmeric and cloves had WBC increase of 050, 300, 050 and 050 c/mcL, respectively. The monocytes increase of the control rats is 125 c/mcL, while the rats fed with basil, moringa, turmeric and cloves had 50, 40, 30 and 53 c/mcL, respectively (Table 6). Table 7 shows the lymphocytes decrease of the control rat is -500 c/mcL, while the lymphocytes decrease of the rats administered basil, moringa, turmeric and cloves are -200, -100, -300 and -290 c/mcL, respectively.

Table 2. Variation in the PVC (%) of the exposed rats.

Group	Day 0	Day 28	Mean Change	MFMER Range
Control	39 ^a ± 2	28 ^b ± 2	-11 ± 3	38.8 - 50
Basil	40 ^a ± 3	35 ^a ± 3	-5 ± 1	38.8 - 50
Moringa	39 ^a ± 2	36 ^a ± 2	-3 ± 1	38.8 - 50
Turmeric	41 ^a ± 3	40 ^a ± 4	-1 ± 1	38.8 - 50
Cloves	40 ^a ± 4	35 ^a ± 3	- 4 ± 2	38.8 - 50

Data are expressed as Mean ± SE;

Mean values with different superscripts 'a' and 'b' along the same row are significantly different at $P < 0.05$; MFMER= Mayo Foundation for Medical Education and Research.

Table 3. Variation in the HB (g/dL) of the exposed rats.

Group	Day 0	Day 28	Mean Change	MFMER Range
Control	13.0 ^a ± 2	09.3 ^b ± 2	- 3.7 ± 3	13.6 - 17.5
Basil	13.3 ^a ± 2	11.6 ^a ± 2	- 1.7 ± 3	13.6 - 17.5
Moringa	13.3 ^a ± 3	12.0 ^a ± 3	-1.3 ± 1	13.6 - 17.5
Turmeric	13.0 ^a ± 2	12.0 ^a ± 2	- 01 ± 0.7	13.6 - 17.5
Cloves	13.3 ^a ± 3	11.6 ^a ± 4	-1.8 ± 1	13.6 - 17.5

Data are expressed as Mean ± SE;

Mean values with different superscripts 'a' and 'b' along the same row are significantly different at P <0.05; MFMER= Mayo Foundation for Medical Education and Research.

Table 4. Variation in the RBC (mc/mcL) of the exposed rats.

Group	Day 0	Day 28	Mean Change	MFMER Range
Control	4.83 ^a ± 0.6	2.93 ^b ± 0.3	-1.91 ± 0.3	4.32 – 5.72
Basil	4.90 ^a ± 0.7	4.00 ^a ± 0.4	- 0.90 ± 0.3	4.32 – 5.72
Moringa	4.85 ^a ± 0.6	4.34 ^a ± 0.5	-1.12 ± 0.1	4.32 – 5.72
Turmeric	4.87 ^a ± 0.8	4.38 ^a ± 0.2	- 0.49 ± 0.1	4.32 – 5.72
Cloves	4.85 ^a ± 0.5	4.36 ^a ± 0.1	- 0.49 ± 0.1	4.32 – 5.72

Data are expressed as Mean ± SE;

Mean values with different superscripts 'a' and 'b' along the same row are significantly different at P <0.05; MFMER= Mayo Foundation for Medical Education and Research.

Table 5. Variation in the WBC (c/mcL) of the exposed rats.

Group	Day 0	Day 28	Mean Change	MFMER Range
Control	4, 600 ^a ± 100	3, 450 ^b ± 100	-1, 150 ± 100	3, 500 – 10, 500
Basil	4, 650 ^a ± 110	4,700 ^a ± 140	050 ± 10	3, 500 – 10, 500
Moringa	4, 500 ^a ± 100	4, 800 ^a ± 200	300 ± 40	3, 500 – 10, 500
Turmeric	4, 550 ^a ± 120	4, 600 ^a ± 100	050 ± 10	3, 500 – 10, 500
Cloves	4, 600 ^a ± 090	4, 650 ^a ± 100	050 ± 0.1	3, 500 – 10, 500

Data are expressed as Mean ± SE;

Mean values with different superscripts 'a' and 'b' along the same row are significantly different at P <0.05; MFMER= Mayo Foundation for Medical Education and Research.

Table 6. Variation in the monocytes (c/ml) of the exposed rats.

Group	Day 0	Day 28	Mean Change	MFMER Range
Control	250 ^a ± 40	375 ^b ± 60	125 ± 20	200 - 600
Basil	250 ^a ± 50	300 ^a ± 40	50 ± 10	200 - 600
Moringa	255 ^a ± 30	295 ^a ± 45	40 ± 10	200 - 600
Turmeric	260 ^a ± 50	290 ^a ± 40	30 ± 09	200 - 600
Cloves	250 ^a ± 40	303 ^a ± 30	53 ± 10	200 - 600

Data are expressed as Mean ± SE;

Mean values with different superscripts 'a' and 'b' along the same row are significantly different at P <0.05; MFMER= Mayo Foundation for Medical Education and Research.

Table 7. Variation in the lymphocytes (c/ml) of the exposed rats.

Group	Day 0	Day 28	Mean Change	MFMER Range
Control	1, 400 ^a ± 100	900 ^b ± 50	-500 ± 60	1, 300 - 4000
Basil	1, 450 ^a ± 090	1, 250 ^a ± 100	-200 ± 50	1, 300 - 4000
Moringa	1, 400 ^a ± 110	1, 300 ^a ± 70	-100 ± 30	1, 300 - 4000
Turmeric	1, 500 ^a ± 100	1, 200 ^a ± 65	-300 ± 70	1, 300 - 4000
Cloves	1, 400 ^a ± 080	1, 110 ^a ± 80	-290 ± 0.1	1, 300 - 4000

Data are expressed as Mean ± SE;

Mean values with different superscripts 'a' and 'b' along the same row are significantly different at P <0.05; MFMER= Mayo Foundation for Medical Education and Research.

4. DISCUSSION

This study was initiated to find an individual-based pollutant exposure management strategy to complement the conventional pollution prevention and control strategies. Pollutants have been reported to produce free radicals in exposed individuals, causing cell and tissue damage, and culminating in a lot of diseases. Fortunately, some medicinal plants, including herbs, vegetables, and spices have been reportedly used in the past to remove free radicals or prevent their oxidative process in the body. These plants have been demonstrated in several studies to contain certain health-promoting nutrients and chemicals.

The marked decrease in the weights and blood parameters of the control rats is an indication of cytotoxic interactions between the rat cells and toxic elements in the POPs. This observation supports the findings of Johnson and Parker [10] and Yahaya *et al.* [11], who separately observed decrease in the weights and blood parameters of rats exposed to industrial pollutants.

POPs contain several toxic chemicals, which varied greatly depending on the source, but generally has organic and inorganic compounds, including sulfate, carbon, heavy metals, among others. These particles can settle directly in the lungs and enter various organs through the circulatory system, causing cellular abnormalities and multi-organ injuries. The WBC in particular, including its subtypes (lymphocytes and monocytes) would ideally strengthen the immune system and fight diseases. So any change in their normal proportions as observed in this study is a sign of serious disease conditions like inflammation, infections, autoimmune diseases, etc.

The almost normal blood parameters and increased weights of the test rats could be attributed to the cell protective and rebuilding properties of the nutrients and antioxidants in the diets administered. A similar result was reported by Janakat and Nassar [12], who observed extract of *Terfezia claveryi* (a species of fungus) almost normalized the effect of carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄) on liver function enzymes of albino rats as a result of the high antioxidants present in the plant. Basil, one of the plants used in the diets formulation, is rich in two flavonoids, namely orientin and vicenin. These two flavonoids have been demonstrated in human white blood cells to protect cell structures as well as chromosomes from radiation and oxidative damage. Basil is also rich in nutrients like vitamin A, vitamin K, folic acid and omega 5 acid, calcium, magnesium, manganese and iron [13]. Moringa contains numerous antioxidants and minerals such as carotenoids-lutein, alpha-carotene, beta-carotene, xanthin, chlorophyll, calcium, zinc, potassium, sodium, magnesium, all the vitamins

and crude protein [14]. The most active ingredient found in turmeric is curcumin and has been reported in several studies to be anti-inflammatory, and can improve organ functions [15-16]. Cloves contain eugenol and flavonoids, such as eugenin, kaempferol, rhamnetin, and eugenitin; all which have been reported for their anti-inflammatory activities. The spice also contains a good amount of health-protecting minerals and vitamins such as potassium, manganese, iron, selenium, magnesium, vitamin A, vitamin B, and vitamin C [17]. The animal feed used in the diets formulation, according to the manufacturers, was fortified with calcium, phosphorus, proteins, and fibers; all which could have contributed to the efficacy of the diets. These nutrients could have lessened the effects of POPs in the control rats too.

5. CONCLUSION

The results of the study show the formulated diets protected the health of the test rats compared with the control. People are therefore advised to include these food plants in their diets to protect them from effects of pollutants. More studies are needed to evaluate the efficacy and health benefits of some other plants.

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